

SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL FEATURES OF QUALIFYING AND EARLY ORIENTATION FOR SPORTS WRESTLING TYPES

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Abstract: This article presents information about the selection methodology and early orientation by types of wrestling (judo, freestyle wrestling, Greco-Roman wrestling, belt wrestling, wrestling), as well as about the age periods of selection by types of wrestling, training features, the role and significance in the selection and orientation of physical qualities.

Keywords: wrestling, qualification, early orientation, questionnaire, survey, judo, freestyle wrestling, Greco-Roman wrestling, belt wrestling, wrestling, methodology, research, results, physical qualities, strength, speed-strength, agility, flexibility, endurance, speed, general, special, physical training.

НАУЧНО-МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ КВАЛИФИКАЦИОННОГО И РАННЕГО ОРИЕНТИРОВАНИЯ ПО ВИДАМ СПОРТИВНОЙ БОРЬБЫ

Аннотация: В статье представлены сведения о методике отбора и раннего ориентирования по видам борьбы (дзюдо, вольная борьба, греко-римская борьба, борьба на поясах, борьба), а также о возрастных периодах отбора по видам борьбы, особенностях подготовки, роль и значение в выборе и направленности физических качеств.

Ключевые слова: борьба, квалификация, раннее ориентирование, анкета, опрос, дзюдо, вольная борьба, греко-римская борьба, борьба на поясах, борьба, методика, исследование, результаты, физические качества, сила, скоростно-силовые, ловкость, гибкость, выносливость, скорость, общая, специальная, физическая подготовка.

Relevance of the topic. The development of recommendations and proposals for the creation and implementation of a methodology for qualifying and early guidance for sports wrestling continues to be one of the most pressing issues facing all sports, not just sports wrestling. The methods used today in sorting and early orientation for sports wrestling do not allow to determine the sorting tasks by assessing the indicators of the physical development, physical qualities, technical and tactical training of wrestlers, the insufficient scientific research work in this direction indicates that they have not been fully studied as a subject of research.

The wrapper of the topic is Kerimov F. from local scientists when drawing up a survey on this topic. A. (2020), Matkarimov R.M. (2015), Usmanxojayev T.S., Aliyev M.B., Sagdiyev H.H., Turdiyev F.K., Akramov J.A., (2006), Salamov R.S. (2015), Halmukhamedov R.D., Shin W.N., Abdurasulova G.B., Tajibaev S.S. (2013), Shakirjanova K.T., Tuxtabayev N.T. (2010), Mirjamolov M.X. (2022), Umarov D.X., Kholmurodov L.Z. (2021), Adilov S.Q. (2018), Nurshin J.M., Mirzakulov Sh.A., Z.S. Artikov (2019), Azizov N.N. (2007), Tastanov N.A., (2017), Olimov M.S. (2019), Dadabayev A.J. (2021) and others used the results of scientific research work.

A number of studies on the topic in the Commonwealth of Independent States and abroad were carried out by Matviyev L.P., (1999), Verkhoshansky Y.V., (2013), Zasiorsky V.M. (2009), Leah V.I. (2000), Matviev L.P. (1999), Azalin N.G. (2008) Guba V.P., Fomin S.G., Chernov S.V. (2006), Fukuda D. Kelly, J. Albuquerque, M. Stout, J. The results of the research work of Hoffman (2017) and many other scientists were used, including studying theoretical data on the basis of a system of sorting and early orientation from textbooks, manuals, monographs, articles and theses,

and on the basis of a study of the current state of the problem in practice, this questionnaire was developed to eliminate this problem.

Based on the scientific and methodological literature and the research carried out and the results obtained from them, the relevance of this topic is based on the following. In particular, on the basis of the analysis and generalization of the studied scientific and methodological literature on the selection and early orientation of sports in our country and the world community in recent years, proposals and recommendations have been made in scientific research on the selection and early orientation of children in sports.

Main part. Based on the analysis of the scientific and methodological literature of the above authors, a survey was carried out with the aim of improving the system and its content of sorting and early orientation to the types of sports wrestling and identifying problems in the study and sorting of its theoretical and practical state. The survey was taken from coaches operating in sports wrestling in Namangan region and the answers were shown in percentages (Table 1).

Table 1.

Results of a questionnaire survey on the treatment of sorting and early orientation of children in sports wrestling

Questionnaire survey questions	Sports wrestling	Indicators of the answers on the account of the total average percentage (%)							
		Answer 1	Percent age	2- Answer	Percent age	Answer 3	Percent age	Answer 4	Percent age
From what age do you think it is better to accept sports wrestling tours?	Judo	6-7 age	23%	8-9 age	22%	10-11 age	36%	12-13 age	19%
	Free Wrestling	6-7 age	26%	8-9 age	24%	10-11 age	38%	12-13 age	12%
	Greek rum wrestling	6-7 age	22%	8-9 age	27%	10-11 age	34%	12-13 age	17%
	Belt wrestling	6-7 age	16%	8-9 age	35%	10-11 age	39%	12-13 age	10%
	Wrestling	6-7 age	19%	8-9 age	24%	10-11 age	44%	12-13 age	13%
What physical qualities do you pay attention to when sorting children into sports wrestling types?	Judo	Fast-power	26%	Durability	37%	Flexibility	15%	Agility	22%
	Free Wrestling	Agility	31%	Fast-power	22%	Durability	26%	Flexibility	21%
	Greek rum wrestling	Flexibility	27%	Fast-power	23%	Agility	17%	Durability	33%
	Belt wrestling	Durability	17%	Agility	25%	Flexibility	29%	Fast-power	29%
	Wrestling	Durability	23%	Flexibility	18%	Fast-power	33%	Agility	26%
What types of preparations Do you use when sorting children into sports wrestling types?	Judo	General physical fitness	43%	Special physical training	27%	Action games that embody the technique of the sport	19%	Functional preparation	11%
	Free Wrestling	Functional preparation	13%	Action games that embody the technique of the sport	18%	General physical fitness	45%	Special physical training	24%

Table 1 continuation									
	Greek rum wrestling	Action games that embody the technique of the sport	15%	Functional preparation	11%	Special physical training	22%	General physical fitness	52%
	Belt wrestling	Functional preparation	12%	General physical fitness	48%	Special physical training	24%	Action games that embody the technique of the sport	16%
	Wrestling	General physical fitness	46%	Functional preparation	13%	Action games that embody the technique of the sport	18%	Special physical training	23%
Do you use strict standards that take into account weight categories when sorting children into sports wrestling types?	Judo	No	8%	Yes	16%	I use in adult wrestlers	57%	Regulatory tests for all weight categories are homogeneous	19%
	Free Wrestling	Yes	11%	Regulatory tests for all weight categories are homogeneous	24%	No	19%	I use in adult wrestlers	46%
	Greek rum wrestling	Regulatory tests for all weight categories are homogeneous	39%	Yes	15%	I use in adult wrestlers	22%	No	24%
	Belt wrestling	Yes	17%	I use in adult wrestlers	35%	No	23%	Regulatory tests for all weight categories are homogeneous	25%
	Wrestling	I use in adult wrestlers	23%	No	29%	Regulatory tests for all weight categories are homogeneous	39%	Yes	9%

The analysis of the survey survey conducted showed that from what age do you think it is better to take sports wrestling? while the content question was reported by Judo Wrestling respondents (23%), 6-7 years old, (22%), 8-9 years old, (36%) 10-11 years old, (19%) 12-13 years old that acceptance had a high effect, free wrestling respondents chose the question (26%) 7-8 years old, (24%) 9-10 years old, (38%), 11-12 years old, (12%) 13-14 years old. Greek rum wrestling was found to be 6-7 years old, (27%) 8-9 years old, (34%) 10-11 years old, (17%) 12-13 years old in this questionnaire questionnaire of respondents. The answers of belt struggle respondents to the above question were reflected in the following indicators, it was found that the respondents (16%) chose 8-9 years, (35%) 10-11 years, (39%), 12-13 years, (10%) 14-15 years. From how old is it acceptable to take the sport of wrestling from what age do you think that the questionnaire in the content reflected in the general indicators of the answers received by the respondents (19%) 7-8 years old, (24%) 9-10 years old, (44%) 11-12 years old, (13%) 13-14 years old.

Figure 1. Distribution of age periods of admission to sports wrestling types

For Example, V.M.Volkov and V.P.Filin sport saralovi is understood as a system of organizational and methodological measures that determine the abilities of children, adolescents and young men and girls in a particular specialty. So we must definitely take saralov to determine the abilities of children for a particular sport. But it was understood that our main goal is to determine the age periods of qualifying us for sports wrestling.

What physical qualities do you pay attention to when sorting children into sports wrestling types in the next questionnaire questionnaire questionnaire? the answers of the respondents to the questionnaire in its content were reflected as follows. This questionnaire was assessed in judokas as (26%) fast-strength, (37%) endurance, (15%) flexibility, (22%) agility quality education. (See Figure 2).

Figure 2. The value of physical qualities when sorting children into sports wrestling types

The answers to this questionnaire on freestyle wrestling were as follows (31%) agility, (22%) fast-strength, (26%) endurance, (21%) flexibility qualities. To the question of what types of training do you use when sorting children into sports wrestling types, it was determined that the respondents in the discipline of judo (43%) pay attention to the general physical fitness, (27%), special physical fitness, (19%) character games that embody the technique of the Sport, (11%) functional training.

In freestyle wrestling, however, the responses of the respondents were assessed as follows (13%) functional training, (18%) eventful games incorporating the technique of the Sport, (45%) general fitness, (24%) special fitness status were found to focus.

The answers of the respondents to this questionnaire on Greek rum wrestling were reflected as follows, in particular (15%) games with character that embody the technique of the Sport, (11%) functional training, (22%) special physical training, (52%) general physical training were found to pay special attention (See Figure 3).

Figure 3. The degree of significance of the types of preparations when sorting children into sports wrestling types

Responses from respondents to this questionnaire survey in the sport of Belt Wrestling were reflected as follows, with (12%) focus on functional training, (48%) on general fitness, (24%) on specific fitness, (16%) on character games incorporating the technique of the Sport.

In wrestling sports, the answers of respondents to this questionnaire questionnaire, on the other hand, were found to pay attention to (46%) general physical fitness, (13%) functional training, (18) character games that embody the technique of the sport, (23%) special physical fitness.

Do you use strict standards that take into account weight categories when sorting children into sports wrestling types? to the question in the content there are no (8%) respondents in the sport of judo, (16%) yes, (57%) I use in adult wrestlers, (19%) have given data on the homogeneity of normative tests for all weight categories (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. The state of use of norms while taking into account weight categories when sorting children into sports wrestling types

In freestyle wrestling, however, the responses of the respondents were evaluated as follows (11%) yes, (24%) the normative tests for all weight categories are homogeneous, (19%) No, (46%) the answers I use in adult wrestlers have been reversed.

The answers of the respondents to this questionnaire on Greek rum wrestling were reflected as follows, in particular (39%) normative tests for all weight categories are homogeneous, (15%) yes, (22%) I use in adult wrestlers, (24%) recorded answers of no content. In the sport of Belt Wrestling, the response of respondents to this questionnaire survey was reflected as follows, (17%) yes, (35%) I use in adult wrestlers, (23%) No, (25%) normative tests for all weight categories have shown homogeneity. In the sport of wrestling, the answers of respondents to this questionnaire, on the other hand (23%) I use in adult wrestlers, (29%) No, (39%) normative tests for all weight categories gave the same, (9%) yes answers.

Conclusion and practical recommendations. Based on the above information, it indicates the need to develop a system based on certain criteria for the selection process for sports wrestling types.

The results of the questionnaire survey, the study of the process of qualifying and early orientation for sports wrestling types are an urgent direction and require further research. Selection and early orientation to sports wrestling, to be considered as a continuous process that covers all the main stages of long-term training, has been proposed by a number of specialists in the field of tobacco. Therefore, at its first stage, it should be expressed in the direction of sports, to identify, evaluate and pragnose the ability of this athlete, and in the process of qualifying, to direct children corresponding to sports wrestling types to this sport. Despite the systematic research carried out, the intensive development of sports wrestling on this topic in educational and methodological sources, new modern approaches in this field require the development of additional scientific, scientific and methodological developments on improving the system and content of qualification for sports wrestling.

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